

FLOODS AND RESULTING LOSSES

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Abstract: At the end of the XIX century - the beginning of the XX century, floods were considered one of the natural disasters in Turkestan. There were various large and small rivers, canals and ditches in Central Asia. Each of them has overflowed its banks in different years due to rains, snowmelt or improper irrigation system. As a result of these natural disasters, the population experienced various losses.

Key words: floods, governorship of Turkestan, military governor of Fergana region, river floods, population problems.

Can be considered in the example of Chust uezd. On May 13 and June 3, 1880, a flood hit the villages of Varzik and Kelyach of Chust uezd. These floods damaged 15 houses in these villages and destroyed 40.5 tons of wheat. As a result, residents of these two villages inform the head of the uezd about these casualties. In addition, residents have drawn up two acts, and these documents indicate the material damage suffered by the villages. In turn, the head of the uezd, through each governor of the region, submitted information to the general governorate of Turkestan about the losses of this natural disaster and asked to pay the damages indicated in the acts. In particular, the military governor of Fergana region estimated the damage caused by water leaks at 600 rubles and asked to compensate them from the budget[1].

In 1876, heavy rains fell in several areas of Andijan uezd, resulting in floods in some villages. As a result of Bunnig, houses in several villages were washed away by water and residents became homeless. One of these villages, Andijan uezd, was a village established for the population relocated from the central parts of the Russian Empire. Although some houses in this village were damaged by a flood in 1876, the colonial administration started practical work on this in 1880. In particular, in June 1880, the military governor of Fergana region wrote to the general-governor

of Turkestan that if the inhabitants of this village are not helped, they will face problems in the coming winter. For this, he asked the central government for 300 rubles[2].

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, people's power was used to eliminate the losses caused by natural disasters. In this case, an alarm was declared among the population and the consequences of the natural disaster were eliminated. We can consider this in the example of 1910. Because it was this year that floods and floods occurred in almost all regions of Turkestan. In particular, the military governors of Syrdarya, Samarkand and Fergana regions and the head of the Amudarya department informed the governor general that floods have occurred in these areas and that the irrigation system has been damaged as a result. Therefore, in 1910, the inhabitants of the village or city who used the ditch had to go out to clean the ditch if the ditch they used was damaged by floods[3]. In this case, each visitor was asked to bring his own working tools. In addition, a special fund was established to eliminate the consequences of the natural disaster, and working tools were purchased from the funds of this fund. Residents who did not have working weapons could use them. Also, if someone does not have the conditions or desire to participate in this hashar, he is exempted from this duty by paying a certain amount of money. There was one condition in this case, it was necessary to pay a certain fee to another person in exchange for this received amount and use it[4].

On the evening of January 11, 1878, heavy rain fell in several volosts of Katta-Kurgan uezd of Samarkand region. As a result of this heavy rain, floods occur in several villages of the uezd. As a result of this flood, casualties occurred in other volosts of Katta-Kurgon uezd. In particular, the head of the Mitani volost sends a report to the head of the Katta-Kurgon uezd on the consequences of heavy rains and floods in January[5]. It can be seen from his report that the flood has washed away many agricultural lands in this region. The head of the volost lists the losses suffered by each village in order. In particular, 50 fields were plowed and 16 fields were not plowed in Orta-Turgun village, 50 fields were plowed and 30 fields were not plowed

in Kichik-Turgun village, 45 fields were plowed and 16 fields were not plowed, in Alankusa village 32 fields were plowed and 20 fields were not plowed and 55 fields in the village of Darunsoy plowed and 30 fields of unplowed agricultural lands were washed away by water[6]. In other villages of Mitan Volost, along with agricultural land, other property of residents was also damaged. For example, in the village of Bovotom-Qorakiya, flood waters washed away 2 mills worth 40 rubles along with 60 fields of plowed land and 90 fields of unplowed land. Another example is Kurli village. In this village, together with 160 acres of agricultural land, 15 tons of bread products and a mill worth 20 rubles were damaged [7].

On April 12, 1878, the head of Shymkent uezd reported to the military governor of the Syrdarya region that several areas of the uezd were flooded and as a result, the population suffered material damage. In turn, the military governor of the region reported to the governor general of Turkestan on May 23 that several parts of Shymkent uezd were flooded in January. It is noted that the Aris, Bugunya and Aksu rivers in the district suddenly and quickly overflowed. As a result of this flood, the population of uezd suffered a total of 29,488 rubles and 5 kopecks of material damage. In his report, the military governor gave the governor general a list of people who lost their properties as a result of floods and asked them to provide financial assistance. In the end, the governor general of Turkestan ordered the Tashkent treasury to give a total of 400 rubles to the residents of Shymkent uezd, who lost their property as a result of the floods in January 1878[8].

In some cases, the causes of urban flooding have been studied. This work was mainly handled by the construction committee of the Turkestan Governor General's Office and their representatives in the regions. Archival documents allow us to research the causes of flooding of the city of Namangan at the end of the 19th century and the measures aimed at preventing them. The city of Namangan was flooded every year and it caused great damage to the city. The Governor-General of Turkestan ordered the Construction Committee to study this situation. On May 30, 1878, the Inspector of the Construction Committee reports to the Governor-General.

In this letter, the inspector states that the floods are caused by the wrong planning of the city of Namangan[9]. The city was located on a slope and the distance between the city and the slope was 30 versts.

As a conclusion, when it rains, the water that falls from this slope is poured into the Ata-Pasho stream that passes through the outskirts of the city. This ditch was narrow but long. However, during heavy rains, water from the slope overflowed the ditch. That is, such a large volume and fast-flowing water was collected in the pits of the Ata-pasha stream and, after filling, suddenly flowed through the slope into the city. These runoff waters were poured into the Yangi-ariq canal, which passed through the city and was used by residents for drinking and watering crops. This large amount of water has washed the banks of the Nyi-arik canal. As a result, the overflowing water from the canal entered the houses and gardens of the residents. The inspector of the construction committee recommends the construction of a dam. This dam was open during heavy rains and was supposed to collect the water from the Yangi-ariq canal. In this case, it is possible to ensure that the banks of the canal are not damaged, and it is possible to prevent flooding.

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